

Fair Housing Ownership and Community Economy

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Presented to the Rhode Island Special Legislative Commission On Housing, tasked by Senate Resolution 1005 (2019) with conducting a comprehensive review of Rhode Island's housing system, for increasing access to safe and affordable housing. Initial findings, recommendations, and potential legislative proposals are due by January 31, 2020, and a final report containing additional recommendations by October 16, 2020, to the President of the Senate.

Disclaimer	2
Context	3
Subtext	4
Summary of Data	6
Summary of Consensus	12
Relief of Housing Security Burden on Community	13
Public Transparency and Accountability	13
Proactive Community Services Management	15
Relief of Housing Security Burden on the Judiciary	15
Access to Case Data	15
Access to the Law	16
Case Assessment and Arbitration	19
Relief of Housing Security Burden on Manager Owners	19
Principle of Investment	19
Means and Merit Income	20
Relief of Housing Security Burden on Tenant Renters	22
Eviction	23
Dispossession	24
Participation	25
Conclusions	26
Policy Priorities	27
Relief for Those Most Burdened	27
Relief for Community Development and Culture	27
Disclosure	28

Disclaimer

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Context

Housing as an asset class is absolutely unique in that it is first and foremost a critical life necessity—a fundamental human right.[¹][²][³] When income does not increase in relation to land and housing prices, people are priced out of their homes and inequality and poverty rise.[⁴] Income deficiency and unconscionable terms beyond one's control, that result in displacement and dispossession, are deceptively cruel forms of imposed economic servitude. Deprivation of the economic means to secure fair housing ownership, healthcare and education, is destructive to human physiology and ecology. Eviction and dispossession is an archaic, highly disruptive, deeply dysfunctional social blight, easily prevented by modern accounting technology. Fair governance is only difficult to achieve when plagued by private conflicts of interest,[⁵] thus, the community is entitled to all subject matter information that implicates access to housing, healthcare, and education. If public information is not made openly available to inform inclusive decision-making, due process and the overlapping consensus required for best outcomes is obstructed. Everyone is safer, freer, healthier and happier when the information we need to know, of which we are part, is openly available and verifiable by the community.[⁶]

¹ Mills, J., Molloy, R., Zarutskie, R. (2019). Large-scale buy-to-rent investors in the single-family housing market: The emergence of a new asset class. *Real Estate Economics*, 47(2), 399-430.

<https://www.investor-realestate-accounts.com/static/uploads/2015084pap.pdf>

² Madden, D., Marcuse, P. (2016). *In Defense of Housing: The Politics of Crisis*. Verso Books.

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/ce1f/62358412c82516473e965fcc7900a6f1efd5.pdf>

³ Alexander, L. T. (2015). Occupying the constitutional right to housing. *Nebraska Law Review*, 94, 245-301.

⁴ George, H. (1879). *Progress and Poverty : An Inquiry into the Cause of Industrial Depressions, and of Increase of Want with Increase of Wealth. The Remedy*. Doubleday & McClure.

⁵ Stein, S. (2019). *Capital City: Gentrification and the Real Estate State*. Verso Books.

⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accountability>

Subtext

While press, paper and grammar books were in limited supply and unavailable to most people in the late 18th century, Adam Smith, a Scottish philosopher of political economy, published *The Theory of Moral Sentiments* (1759) and *The Wealth of Nations* in 1776. Smith struggled unsuccessfully to reconcile progress and poverty, and spilled inkwells of ink lamenting the injustices and market instability of what he called, “commercial society,” settling for a moral sentiment compromise: “they who feed, clothe, and lodge the whole body of the people, should have such a share of the produce of their own labor as to be themselves tolerably well fed, clothed, and lodged.”^[7]

Smith is most popularly known for making an obscure reference to "trickling down" and an "invisible hand." Remarkably, 250 years later, in the digital age of computer science and information technology, there are some who still say that poverty is inevitable; that it must continue indefinitely, and that magically, vis-à-vis an "invisible hand" that sprinkles around some "trickling down" from unseen places, an upper ruling class rides on the backs of an underclass through a dreamland of a life worth living.^[8] A more influential and disruptive thinker and analyst of the same period called it slavery.^[9]

Thomas Paine (*Common Sense*, 1776) observed first hand the Iroquois and other First American communities living in economic harmony with ecology in a federated free society organized by inclusive decision-making, where everyone was equally sheltered, clothed, watered, fed and informed. The First Americans were more advanced in agriculture, forestry, wildlife management, and pharmacopeia than the invading Christians who destroyed them with their guns, germs and steel, like the billions of Passenger Pigeon into extinction, and nearly the buffalo.^[10]

The First Americans occupied the same land for over 12 thousand years before being decimated from 15 million to just 300,000 (3 million descendants today) in the most horrific genocide the earth has ever buried, but could not cover up. The *Indian Givers* gave us everything the Europeans didn't have at the time, or didn't destroy, including a

⁷ Rasmussen, D. (2016, June 9). The problem with inequality, according to Adam Smith: the allure of extreme wealth can contort human sympathies, causing the public to admire the wealthy and shun the poor. *The Atlantic*.

<https://www.theatlantic.com/business/archive/2016/06/the-problem-with-inequality-according-to-adam-smith/486071/>

⁸ Kennedy, G. (2009). Adam Smith and the invisible hand: From metaphor to myth. *Econ Journal Watch*, 6(2), 239-263.

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Paine

¹⁰ Dunbar-Ortiz, R. (2015). *An Indigenous People's History of the United States*, Beacon Press.

better working example of federated land-use governance.^[11] The First American system of federated governance was adopted in part by the invading aristocracy, although never formally acknowledged by the Second Americans. We should not deceive ourselves in our dreams and accomplishments that any of us ever made it here on our own, or where we'll go when we're gone.^[12]

Paine understood first hand that the invisible hand attributed to Smith is unseen simply because it does not exist as a cogent system of governance or business management logic (*Age of Reason*, 1794). He reasoned that financial inequality results from politically created money, financialized to impose economic scarcity (sanctions), economic exclusion (sanctions), and the undemocratic distribution of ownership (sanctions), and that the myth that "the poor shall be with you always" is dispelled by the fact that there are numerous management and accounting methods available to decision-makers everywhere to avoid such unnecessary economic dysfunction;^[13] that it is in the best interest of all participants that rules of economy not be left to invisible forces of chance and deep state secrecy: *Agrarian Justice* (1797), prior to the industrial slave mills, the USPS Pony Express, the camera, the telegraph, and the continental railway that transported journalists and researchers from shore to shore to verify what was going down on the ground we all live on.

Paine concluded that for an economy to function fairly using the public creation and issuance of money as a means of production in society, everyone should receive a Citizen's Dividend in the first instance, and most equally and fairly as necessary on a regular basis from their common interest and participation in the economic production of society.^[14]

By the late 19th century, about the same time Alexander Graham Bell made the first long distance phone call, an American economist and policy analyst by the name of Henry George, published *Progress and Poverty*.^[15] With more technology and data at his disposal than was available to Smith or Paine 100 years earlier, *Progress and Poverty* established concretely that land and housing are uniquely different from other asset

¹¹ Weatherford, J. (1988). *Indian Givers: How the Indians of the Americas Transformed the World*. Crown Publishers.

¹² "...this idea of the gift-giving Indian helping to establish and enrich the development of the United States is an insidious smoke screen meant to obscure the fact that the very existence of the country is a result of the looting of an entire continent and its resources." (Dunbar-Ortiz, p. 5)

¹³ Today it is technically elementary to network the world's inputs and outputs and use opensource business management and accounting software, running on opensource hardware, universally available for inclusive public decision-making, i.e., a wikipedia for humus.io |See example: <https://decidim.org/>

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citizen%27s_dividend

¹⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_George

classes, in that the earth and our living ecosystem is a common resource upon whose biodiversity we each equally depend for food and shelter. In exchange for one's exclusive use of land location, he insisted, one must reciprocate par value to the community and environment, thus balancing our economic relationship to each other and our ecosystem as the First Americans before had long recognized and demonstrated.

Henry George wrote about land resource economics in such a novel way that even cognitive dissonance gave way. If land and housing are allowed to be held absentee to sell for a passive capital gain in the future, while holding it vacant or for rent to one's neighbor or friend, it will increase the cost of access to a fundamental human necessity, and will have cyclically destructive effects on the economy and society over time. If the incomes of the majority do not increase in proportion to the money extracted from the economy by a minority class of absentee home speculators, who can afford to buy and hold vacant, or extract the real costs of ownership (maintenance) from a tenant-class, low income and middle class families will be priced out of the market, off the land, and out of their homes, creating greater wealth disparity, income inequality and poverty with every financialized cycle of imposed scarcity. As wage-salary incomes fall further below the cost of living, more people are less able to purchase goods and services from small business owners and they go down too, chipping further into the middle class while poverty increases.

Summary of Data

Everyone blames everyone and almost no one seems to know for sure what happened, although, a half century of computing technology, developed at public expense, contains the public data needed for everyone to know and understand what happened. Yet, the public today must try to piece it together bit by bit and pay to access most public data. [16] A summary of data available to the public, surrounding the 2008 crisis, looks something like this:

- A. By 2007 median income had fallen far behind the median cost of living, so mortgage companies relaxed terms on first mortgages and wrote second and third equity loans, and buy-back refinance loans, based on rising housing bubble valuations.[17]

¹⁶ Schmitt, J. (Producer), Schmitt, J. (Director). (2018). *Paywall: The Business of Scholarship* [Motion Picture]: United States. <https://paywallthemovie.com/>

¹⁷ Jurow, K. (2018, June 18). Will re-defaults of mortgage modifications undermine housing markets? *Advisor Perspectives*. <https://www.advisorperspectives.com/articles/2018/06/18/will-re-defaults-of-mortgage-modifications-underscore-housing-markets.pdf>

- B. Homeowners default and redefault in record numbers.^[18]
- C. The corporate nation-state responds by creating \$500 billion in new money to financialize the bailout of private Capital, too-big-to-fail banks, equity firms, mortgage companies and industry corporations, et al.^[19]
- D. Equity firms then move in to buy up and artificially shore up real estate and housing prices, bulk purchasing single family homes in record numbers, as more homeowners are displaced and dispossessed, and turned again into feudal renters. Equity firms now have the largest holdings of single family houses for rent; which in the 1950s and into the 70s and 80s could be purchased on a 15 year mortgage and paid for on the average single "breadwinner" income.^[20]
- E. To keep real estate prices high, mortgage companies kept houses off the market by holding them vacant and writing loan modifications; then modified the loans again after redefault, multiple times on many of the same properties, where occupants in redefault have remained in overpriced houses for years, without payment and with no intention of paying off the mortgage.^[21]
- F. New absentee home buyers have been enticed by corporate media into believing that there are always passive capital gains to be made in holding and renting single family homes, and now 45% of absentee homeowners own only one rental home. Nearly 90% are owned by absentee landlords whose total portfolio consists of fewer than ten homes.^[22]

¹⁸ See note [17]

¹⁹ Harbert, T. (2019, Feb 21). Here's how much the 2008 bailouts really cost. *MIT Management Sloan School*. <https://mitsloan.mit.edu/ideas-made-to-matter/heres-how-much-2008-bailouts-really-cost>

²⁰ Semuels, A. (2019, February 19). When Wall Street is your landlord. *The Atlantic*. <https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2019/02/single-family-landlords-wall-street/582394/>

²¹ Jurow, K. (2019, March 19). Why out-of-control bubble-era mortgages still threaten to smash major U.S. housing markets. *MarketWatch*. <https://www.marketwatch.com/story/this-bubble-era-mortgage-trick-could-smash-major-us-housing-markets-2019-03-18>

²² Jurow, K. (2019, August 15). Here's the real reason why U.S. home prices haven't been demolished. *MarketWatch*. <https://www.marketwatch.com/story/heres-the-real-reason-why-us-home-prices-havent-been-smashed-2019-08-14>

- G. Bulk auction buyers have engaged in various \$1 quit deed swaps and other dark money strategies to grab every bit of capital they can squeeze from homeownership in the new feudalism of single family home rentals.^[23]
- H. The actions of the mortgage and equity industry to keep homes off the market and property prices inflated, served to increase vacancies to 5.8 million in 2016, and increased rents by 31%, all while household incomes remain at crisis-level lows.^{[24][25][26]}
- I. In 2017, adjusted for inflation, median household income in the U.S. had risen only 14% over the previous thirty years, while housing costs rose 290%, healthcare costs 51%, and tuition at public four-year colleges up 311%. Median income is at a record low relative to housing, healthcare and education costs; which explains why household debt and consumer unsecured debt is at an all-time high.^[27]
- J. It follows that eviction filings are also at all-time highs of about 2.5 million per year, and the eviction crisis now looks a lot like the 2008 mortgage crisis that remains in crisis; and it is estimated that “for every eviction executed through the courts, there are two more that effectively occur outside formal judicial processes.”^[28]
- K. In 2018, reportedly 8000 households in Rhode Island, men, women and children, (28 households per day) were forced by eviction, or threat of eviction, into costly disruptive relocation, transitional homelessness, or homelessness.^[29]
- L. The final blow to the community is the dispossession and liquidation of personal property as a result of eviction, feeding a moving and storage industry that proliferated around us while we slept inside our housing bubble, exacerbated by

²³ Akers, J., Seymour, E. (2019). The eviction machine: neighborhood instability and blight in Detroit's neighborhoods. *Poverty Solutions Research Publications*, University of Michigan. <https://poverty.umich.edu/working-paper/the-eviction-machine-neighborhood-instability-and-blight-in-detroits-neighborhoods-2/>

²⁴ Florida, Richard. (2018, July 27). Vacancy: America's other housing crisis. *CityLab*.

<https://www.citylab.com/equity/2018/07/vacancy-americas-other-housing-crisis/565901/>

²⁵ Harrison, P., Kraemer, H. (2019). Homes for all: The progressive 2020 agenda for housing. *Data for Progress*. Accessed May 16, 2019. http://filesforprogress.org/reports/homes_for_all.pdf

²⁶ Lincoln Institute of Land Policy. (2018). The Empty House Next Door: Understanding and Reducing Vacancy and Hypervacancy in the United States.

<https://www.lincolnst.edu/sites/default/files/pubfiles/empty-house-next-door-full.pdf>

²⁷ Smith, Y. (2019, August 2). Families drowning in debt to stay in the middle class. *Naked Capitalism*.

<https://www.nakedcapitalism.com/2019/08/families-drowning-in-debt-to-stay-in-the-middle-class.html>

²⁸ Desmond, M. (2016). *Evicted: Poverty and Profit in the American City*. Crown Publishers.

²⁹ Evicted Rhode Island: a Roadmap to Reforming the Rhode Island Eviction System. *Signs of Providence*. <http://evicted-in-ri.com/>

predatory litigation for extra bounty from low and middle income families, especially in eviction cases where there is no delinquency and the landlord is trying to time the market to take capital gains at the top, forcing tenants to the street when home prices and rents are highest and housing is least available; where renters start over again from the bottom, saddled with a double or triple moving and storage bill for their personal property foisted on them by eviction, often resulting in liquidation for pennies of what it cost them.^[30]^[31]

The reception of Henry George's *Progress and Poverty* was unparalleled, and his work was well received the world over. By 1936, it had been translated into thirteen languages and at least six million copies had been sold. Its influence on Denmark, the United Kingdom, Australia, and New Zealand was immense.^[32] In American dreamland, though, the common sense of *Progress and Poverty* was no match for the get-rich-quick rush of the roaring twenties... until the collapse. An emergency New Deal was struck to prevent civil unrest and all-out violence, but the 1929 crash-deal never got to the crux of class inequality caused by land and housing speculation and unfair distribution of income, i.e., *Progress and Poverty* also called for a citizen's dividend to balance monetarily the absence of employee ownership, and insufficient income. Most New Deal gains toward income equality and economic mobility have been lost, and here we are again at levels of wealth disparity and housing insecurity not seen since the 1930s.^[33]

Denmark, with over three times the population density of the U.S., recognized that *Progress and Poverty* is as important as it gets, and today has nearly one hundred percent participation in their economy and public decision-making, where everyone has access to quality healthcare and education, is securely housed, well fed and informed.^[34]

³⁰ See [Disclosure](#); Riquier, A. (2019, March 30). The eviction crisis is starting to look a lot like the subprime mortgage crisis. *MarketWatch*.
<https://www.marketwatch.com/story/the-eviction-crisis-is-starting-to-look-a-lot-like-the-subprime-crisis-2019-03-26>

³¹ The Storage & Warehouse Leasing Industry comprised over 60,000 businesses in 2019, grossed a total revenue of \$39 bn and had an annual growth of 3.1% from 2014-2019. (IBISWorld. (July 2019). Locked in: Low rental vacancies have paved the way for high demand for storage units.
<https://www.ibisworld.com/united-states/market-research-reports/storage-warehouse-leasing-industry/>

³² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Progress_and_Poverty

³³ Florida, R. (2019, August 1). The double whammy: housing and income inequality. *CityLab*.
<https://www.citylab.com/equity/2019/08/home-prices-jobs-inequality-economic-mobility-data-research/594829/>

Florida, R. (2019, May 9). 'Build more housing' is no match for inequality. *CityLab*.
<https://www.citylab.com/equity/2019/05/housing-supply-home-prices-economic-inequality-cities/588997/>

See also: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/New_Deal

³⁴ Birth rates decline and crime disappears in populations that share an equally comfortable and secure standard of living: <https://borgenproject.org/poverty-and-overpopulation/>

Together with their Scandinavian neighbors they have the highest levels of equality, economic security, and overall quality of life of any region in the world.^[35] From the increase in productivity and efficiencies of computing and machine technology, the Prime Minister of Finland, like many other thought-leaders today, recognize that there is a huge surplus of minds with plenty of time on their trickle-down hands to easily manage and maintain their 24/7 infrastructure and robust economy on a four day work week of six hours per day.^[36] Whatever criticisms the Scandinavians endure, they don't suffer the same shameful indignity of human exclusion, inequality and housing insecurity, or lack of access to healthcare and education extant in the American Dream, where as the late George Carlin used to say, "...you have to be asleep to believe it."^[37]

The U.K., although in close geographic proximity to their Scandinavian brethren, imposes extreme economic inequality and hardship on their society, similar in scope to the United States. Identified in U.K. research are the same fundamentals that absentee housing ownership as an asset class cannot perform both as a wealth generator for passive capital and conversely provide fair housing ownership for all members of society. The proven alternative is to follow Scandinavia's example and work toward economic policies that include everyone most fairly in the economy, using open public data to inform equal participation in one's own fair housing.^[38]^[39]

Presumably all of the estimated 2.5 million families and individuals in the U.S. who are forced into transitional homelessness each year by eviction filings, (living in campers, on the street, in rundown expensive hotel rooms, or burdening family or friends) and most, if not all, of the half million American homeless each year—including 40 thousand veterans— have a trickle-down cell phone or a trickle-down smartphone, and it is estimated that 42% of those homeless even have a trickle-down job that doesn't pay a trickle-down income to cover the real cost of trickle-down living.^[40]

³⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_Progress_Index

³⁶ Teivainen, A. (2019, August 19). Marin floats idea of a four-day, 24-hour work week. *Helsinki Times*. <https://www.helsinkitimes.fi/finland/finland-news/domestic/16663-marin-floats-idea-of-a-four-day-24-hour-work-week.html>

³⁷ Berry, B. (2011, March 19). George Carlin knew why they call it 'the American Dream.' *The Capital Times (Wisconsin)*. <https://www.commondreams.org/views/2011/03/19/george-carlin-knew-why-they-call-it-american-dream>

³⁸ Hearne, R. (2017). A home or a wealth generator? Inequality, financialisation and the Irish housing crisis. http://mural.maynoothuniversity.ie/12052/1/RH_Home%20oor.pdf

³⁹ Dent Coad, E. (2017). After Grenfell: Housing and inequality in Kensington and Chelsea: "The most unequal borough in Britain." <https://justice4grenfell.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/364307729-After-Grenfell.pdf>

⁴⁰ "Of the approximately 3.5 million people who experience homelessness in the United States each year, 42% are working at least part-time, an indication that their incomes are insufficient to afford decent and

The idea that we can solve a systemic national crisis of fundamental monetary dysfunction by debating on Facebook and Twitter an 18th century invisible hand theory attributed to Adam Smith, i.e., “The establishment of perfect justice, of perfect liberty, and of perfect equality, is the very simple secret which most effectively secures the highest degree of prosperity to all the three classes,” is cogently absurd, given the fact that it is technically trivial to use the same computing technology of Surveillance Capitalism's "social" media to manage full inclusion and participation in fair housing ownership, healthcare, and education, in which all have an equal interest and right.[⁴¹]
[⁴²]

In May of 1877, less than two years before Henry George released *Progress and Poverty*, an arbitrary ultimatum was issued to the Nimíipuu (Nez Perce) by General Oliver Otis Howard in the form of a Thirty Day Eviction Notice, demanding that nearly eight hundred (800) men, women and children, and elderly, together with their herds of hundreds of livestock, and homes and belongings, vacate their homeland of twelve thousand years.[⁴³] The terms were impossible. Sound familiar? Failure to vacate, Howard said, would be considered an act of war against the U.S. Government. In practice, it was a merciless declaration of genocide under the pretense that God had promised the land occupied from the beginning by the Nimíipuu, to the invading Christians. Although, in the real world, it was just another of many in the long trail of abuses of power, blatant violations of treaty law and every concept of due process fairness precedent in that tragic May of 1877.

Chief Joseph pleaded for more time, and when his fellow councilman, Chief Toohulhulsote, voiced alarm over Howard's insane edict, he was jailed for five (5) days to further pressure the Nez Perce into abandoning their property and homeland without due process, and to surrender to imprisonment at one of the reservation internment camps where the last of the few remaining survivors of the 15 million First Americans were already confined.[⁴⁴]

Toohulhulsote described his people's genocide by the invaders before he was shot to death on Bear Paw Mountain: "Part of the Indians gave up their land. I never did. The

safe permanent housing.” Universal Livable Income. *National Coalition for the Homeless*.
https://www.nationalhomeless.org/advocacy/universal_livable_incomes.html

⁴¹ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power*. PublicAffairs. (See YouTube interviews.)

⁴² Lincoln Institute of Land Policy | <https://www.lincolninst.edu/>

⁴³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nez_Perce_people

⁴⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chief_Joseph

earth is part of my body, and I never gave up the earth," echoing Thomas Paine one hundred years before; "the earth, in its natural uncultivated state... was the common property of the human race." Joseph, who had always advocated democracy and non-violence, said it best: "The earth and myself are of one mind. The measure of the land and the measure of our bodies are the same." The Christian aggressors, however, failed to grasp or accept the implications of their own creation myth: "from dust thou art to dust thou shalt return."^[45]

The Nez Perce were ultimately faced with only three options in response to being outnumbered and overpowered by the invading law breakers: either fight, or flee, or flow, and they did all three most honorably and valiantly, appealing tirelessly, some say miraculously,^[46] to the rule of law under the logic of due process ecology:

Tears like falling rain slake the thirst and douse the flames, and cooling in the crucible an idea forms; a nugget of belief in the hearts of the poor that maybe in the dawn's new light they have a right to the law. — Ça Ira, (opera) by Roger Waters, Pink Floyd, 2005.

Summary of Consensus

Overlapping consensus is clearly evident in the emerging international body of core logic literature,^[47] which aligns consistently with what the First Americans, Thomas Paine, Henry George and many others have shown, and the data proves:

- A. If money is used for economy, then how money is created, how it is issued in the first instance, how much is distributed to all participants, and how it is accounted for in production and throughout the economy, is of paramount importance to an ecology of sustainable governance.
- B. If fair housing ownership (land), healthcare (medical/pharmacopeia) and access to education (personal development) is controlled by passive capital for private capital gains, then private capital must also provide the means and accounting for

⁴⁵ Ironically, the logic of earth as commons under Judeo-Christian religious law was argued in 1999 under feudal law in Scotland to defend eviction proceedings against up to 90 low income or unemployed Glasgow families, in the homeland of Adam Smith. Interestingly, no citation was made to commons per Acts 2:44-45, Acts 4:32, and Acts 5:1-11. — McIntosh, A. (2007). The case for god: carbeth hutters' feudal defence against eviction. *Journal for the Study of Religion, Nature and Culture*, 5(1).

http://www.alastairmcintosh.com/articles/2000_carbeth.htm

⁴⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nez_Perce_War

⁴⁷ Not to be confused with CoreLogic, the dominant U.S. company with privileged access to acquire and disseminate public data and influence housing markets behind their monster paywall.

how private capital and everyone else is to secure equal access and ownership interest to meet these fundamental individual human needs most fairly.

- C. Whatever the rules we choose for how to manage our economy, openly verifiable accounting for the resources required to live securely and comfortably in an openly free and fair society must be available to everyone for inclusive public decision-making.
- D. Our ability to openly account for resources and participation with network computing technology far exceeds exponentially the limited bookkeeping and storage methods available in 1776, in 1879, in 1929, even in 1968, with the Fair Housing Act; but not in 2008 or in 2020, and we are now without excuse for withholding public information for public decision-making.
- E. We know beyond any doubt today that the destructive forces of unseen hands and unpredictable trickle-down is caused by a plain lack of open access and accounting for the data needed to inform inclusive participation and fair ownership.

Relief of Housing Security Burden on Community

Public Transparency and Accountability

Community governance is disempowered when in practice it is impossible to know or comply with the law; when it is irrational and cannot be administered fairly to achieve its stated purpose and intent. We cannot know with certainty how fair or functional the law is or how our proposed legislation to improve policy will work, without the data. What we know for certain is that rules of law permitting eviction and dispossession are archaically feudal and abusive, and we are routinely denied due process sufficient to secure fair housing interests and our personal property,^[48] primarily because we do not have open access to the data needed to inform due process and inclusive decision-making, including but not limited to the following data and systems:

1. Vacant housing and property conditions, and listing of all mortgaged properties in default; all single-family homes rented by mortgage and equity firms, and number of homes and apartments each absentee homeowner owns, to accurately

⁴⁸ Schmidt, Breezy A. (2017). North Dakota case study: the eviction mill's fast track to homelessness. *North Dakota Law Review* 92(3), pp. 595-642.

account for shortages and surplus housing, and to plan and fund fair housing rehab and construction for shared ownership and management, i.e., public-private land trust cooperatives, etc..^[49]

2. The number of forced relocations and evictions, and the parties involved; in order to immediately take action to mitigate the impact on individuals, families and our economy and healthcare system.^[50]
3. Liquidation numbers and the parties involved in the sale and purchase of personal property in the moving and storage rental market; to immediately halt the practice and its impact on individuals, families and our economy and healthcare system.^[51]
4. A public Housing Data System (HDS), for personal and business accounts to access property data and report property issues, list vacant and available housing, verify income and process standardized applications and agreements, autoselect qualified applicants by sortition to prevent discrimination, and to file annual means statements with respect to public subsidization, etc..^[52]
5. Preservation and publication of all eviction and property liquidation records so as to not compromise important historic data, supported by legislation prohibiting discrimination on the basis of source of income or prior evictions, except on clear and convincing evidence of a need for special housing.^[53]
6. Immediate requirement that all public data be made openly accessible to the public via opensource API, in the interim to full deployment of a Housing Data System, so that researchers and the public can query the data and participate in opensource development of the HDS.

⁴⁹ Vacant Property Research Network | <https://vacantpropertyresearch.com/>

⁵⁰ Hirsch, E. L. (2018) How to End Long-Term Homelessness in Rhode Island. *HousingWorks RI* at Roger Williams University.

http://www.housingworksri.org/Portals/0/Uploads/Documents/HWRI-SS_How%20to%20End%20Long-Term%20Homelessness_2018-Nov.pdf

⁵¹ R.I.G.L. § 9-26-4 and § 9-26-12 prohibits the liquidation of personal property as, “exempt from attachment on any warrant of distress or on any other writ, original, mesne, or judicial.”

⁵² The rental application process is completely unregulated with regard to fees, qualification criteria and selection secrecy, and is facially unfair, with no provision to prevent discrimination.

See <https://www.randomizer.org/links/> and platform example: <https://decidim.org/>

⁵³ Trangle, S. (2019) New York tenants worry new blacklist ban won't be enforced. *amNEWYORK*. <https://www.amny.com/real-estate/tenant-blacklist-ban-1.33255395/>

Proactive Community Services Management

The cost to secure fair housing ownership for all members of society, through economic inclusion and accountability of all participants, will always be significantly less than the quality of life consequences and cost to the economy that result from unfair displacement, dispossession, and insufficient income to meet the cost of living, accrue savings, and to purchase non-critical products and services that local businesses depend on selling to stay in business.

1. Preemptively assess housing conditions and availability, together with the cost-income burden of each party, on a case by case basis for good faith cause, before any eviction judgement can be issued.^[54]
2. Align fair housing legislation and administrative policy with the economic reality that fair housing ownership interest and living income, together with healthcare, education and savings benefits, in exchange for equal participation, are fundamental human needs and rights.^[55]

Relief of Housing Security Burden on the Judiciary

Access to Case Data

Rhode Island court case documents are currently stored in the Electronic Filing System (EFS) database, provided by the proprietary software company, Tyler Technologies, Inc., at an initial contract cost to Rhode Island in 2013 of 6 million dollars.^[56] All court case documents are deemed public except for narrowly defined privacy information that must be redacted per R.I. Pub. Ac. R. 4.. Public case information contained in the EFS database is not currently made available to the public to query by case type and other relevant search criteria. One may only search by individual case number or by the name of a party to a case. The public remains completely in the dark as to parties involved and the number of case types filed in our courts, with no way to ascertain how the number of

⁵⁴ Why do we need protections against evictions in New York State? (2019). *Housing Justice For All*. <https://www.housingjusticeforall.org/goodcause>

⁵⁵ Rhode Island was the first State to recognize, in part, housing security as a fundamental human right. R.I.G.L. § 34-37.1-2. Homeless Bill of Rights. Legislative intent: “(1) At the present time, many persons have been rendered homeless as a result of economic hardship, a severe shortage of safe, affordable housing, and a shrinking social safety net.”

⁵⁶ Tyler Technologies signs \$6 million contract with the state of Rhode Island judiciary. (2013, April 9). *Business Wire* via *The Motley Fool*, AOL.com. <https://www.aol.com/2013/04/09/tyler-technologies-signs-6-million-contract-with-t/>

various case types might impact our personal choices and community, and inform public policy. There is very little cost, if any, involved in making public case information openly available on the six million dollar machine, augmented by open API. However, the socioeconomic cost of not making public court case information available is well known to be catastrophically high, i.e., secret court proceedings always accompany the worst forms of corruption and violence.

1. It is estimated that three out of five civil cases involve a self-represented person. [57] Currently pro se litigants —unless they are attorneys— do not have electronic access to the court documents in their own cases, and formal requests by pro se defendants to the courts in Rhode Island for electronic access by data subscription are summarily denied.[58]
2. The burden on court facilities, road traffic impact, and the burden on employers and employees due to travel and other time requirements to access and pay for the printing of case documents at the courthouse in person, implicates due process and is costly and irrational in 2020. [59]

Access to the Law

There is currently a trend to provide right to counsel to low income individuals in eviction cases. Philadelphia claims that a \$3.5 million investment in Right to Counsel would save the city \$45.2 million sometime down the line. New York City estimated the program would save \$300 million a year, and in 2017 became the first city to pass this legislation.[60] Everyone deserves access to the law and legal assistance of choice as a

⁵⁷ The Self-Represented Litigation Network | <https://www.srln.org/>

⁵⁸ See [Disclosure](#); Rhode Island Judiciary Data Subscription Agreement (Revised October 1, 2019). https://www.courts.ri.gov/efiling/PDF/Data_Subscription_Agreement.pdf

⁵⁹ “The Public, self-represented litigants, and parties shall have Remote Access to the register of actions or Docket but shall not have Remote Access to other Electronic Case Information.” (Rhode Island Judiciary Rules Of Practice Governing Public Access To Electronic Case Information, 08/01/2018)

⁶⁰ Capps, K. (2017, August 14). New York City guarantees a lawyer to every resident facing eviction. *CityLab*.

<https://www.citylab.com/equity/2017/08/nyc-ensures-eviction-lawyer-for-every-tenant/536508/>

Ross, S. R. (2018, November 13). Economic Return on Investment of Providing Counsel in Philadelphia Eviction Cases for Low-Income Tenants. Prepared for the Philadelphia Bar Association’s Civil Gideon and Access to Justice Task Force.

<https://www.philadelphiabar.org/WebObjects/PBA.woa/Contents/WebServerResources/CMSResources/PhiladelphiaEvictionsReport.pdf>

fundamental right to due process.^[61] For this very reason, ironically, there are more than budgetary concerns regarding right to counsel funding and how it relates to the lack of due process involved in the feudal practice of eviction and dispossession:

1. Recall that the U.S. criminal justice system has built the world's largest prison industry on plea bargains that are negotiated in 97% of cases where a public defender has been appointed. ^[62]^[63]
2. Right to counsel does not address the legislation and administrative policies needed to prevent eviction and dispossession, which reduces the need for counsel.
3. Right to counsel is not a direct investment in a living income and fair housing economy, where feudal evictions are not permitted, compulsory process would be rare, and dispossession only a reminder of past human rights abuses.^[64]
4. Right to counsel does not provide an attorney to those who are not indigent, adding to the pro se stigma that serves to pressure those who do not qualify for court-appointed counsel to hire an attorney and "plea-bargain" a settlement, wherein they are forced to bear the cost of relocation anyway. The crisis of fast-food evictions feeds attorneys, landlords, and the moving and storage industry; and with or without counsel all renters are at risk of predatory eviction and dispossession. Renters with more resources and garnishable incomes make easier targets for predatory practices and are more at risk.^[65]
5. Once in the eviction fast-food line there is little time to find counsel suited to the task of addressing due process issues and willing to take the case on acceptable

⁶¹ Earth Compact 2020. *Humus.io*.

<https://sites.google.com/humus.io/home/projects/earth-compact-2020>

⁶² Yoffe, E. (2017, September). Innocence is irrelevant: this is the age of the plea bargain—and millions of Americans are suffering the consequences. *The Atlantic*.

<https://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/2017/09/innocence-is-irrelevant/534171/>

⁶³ The Innocence Project (2018, August 17). Report: Guilty Pleas on the Rise, Criminal Trials on the Decline.

<https://www.innocenceproject.org/guilty-pleas-on-the-rise-criminal-trials-on-the-decline/>

⁶⁴ Jay Martin, director of the Community Housing Improvement Program, a group that represents building owners and managers in NYC, said that “instead of taking a victory lap” on right to counsel and other reforms NYC should be focused “on developing more affordable housing.”

<https://www.nydailynews.com/new-york/ny-evictions-rent-laws-legal-aid-20200106-juiw2tbqqfhu3eyniou2hskkni-story.html>

⁶⁵ Immergluck, D., Ernsthausen, J., Earl, S., Powell, A. (2019). Multifamily evictions, large owners, and serial filings: Findings from metropolitan Atlanta. 10.13140/RG.2.2.24976.05120.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331877056_Multifamily_Evictions_Large_Owners_and_Serial_Filings_Findings_from_Metropolitan_Atlanta

terms.^[66] The solution points clearly to open public access to the law and effective due process where tenants are heard on the merits of the case, i.e., the Rhode Island District and Superior Court Rules of Procedure, with annotations, are not available to the public online. Five years ago, in 2015, the Conference of Chief Justices (CCJ) and Conference of State Court Administrators (COSCA) launched a "Justice for All Initiative" to provide technical assistance to states for reaching a 100% access goal. The goal is far from being met and cannot be reached unless the public has ubiquitous online access to the law and case documents to openly account for due process in our courts. In 2020 no one should be forced to bear the cost of time and environmental impact of travel to visit a library terminal in order to get online access to the law.^[67]

6. Right to counsel does not provide open access to the law or due process, and serves to perpetuate attorney and court bias against self-represented parties. Court procedure is manipulated and circumvented by attorneys with impunity, and judges have immunity. Court bias against pro se litigants, unless they are attorneys, is openly obvious and acknowledged by federal judges and bar associations.^[68] Even represented tenants who refuse to sign a Stipulation "plea-bargain," are denigrated. The problem is epidemic.^[69] Maryland District Court Judge Dorothy J. Wilson and Judge Miriam B. Hutchins, point to the

⁶⁶ McKenzie, S., Dougherty, A. (2004). Fast food justice: the denial of tenants' due process rights in Chicago's eviction courts. *Public Interest Law Reporter*, 1-5.

<http://lawcommons.luc.edu/pilr/vol9/iss2/2>

⁶⁷ Conference of Chief Justices, Conference of State Court Administrators. (2015). Resolution 5: Reaffirming the Commitment to Meaningful Access to Justice for All.

https://www.ncsc.org/~media/Microsites/Files/access/5%20Meaningful%20Access%20to%20Justice%20for%20All_final.ashx

Center on Court Access to Justice for All. (2013). Ensuring the Right to Be Heard for Self-Represented Litigants: Modules for Judges.

<https://www.ncsc.org/microsites/access-to-justice/home/curriculum.aspx>

⁶⁸ Weiss, D. C. (2017, September 11). Posner: Most judges regard pro se litigants as 'kind of trash not worth the time.' *ABA Journal*.

http://www.abajournal.com/news/article/posner_most_judges_regard_pro_se_litigants_as_kind_of_trash_nor_worth_the_time

Conference of Chief Justices, Conference of State Court Administrators. (2012, July 25). Resolution 2: In Support of Expanding Rule 2.2 of the ABA Model Code of Judicial Conduct to Reference Cases Involving Self-Representing Litigants.

<https://ccj.ncsc.org/~media/Microsites/Files/CCJ/Resolutions/07252012-Support-Expanding-Rule-ABA-Model-Code-Judicial-Conduct-Self-Representing-Litigants.ashx>

⁶⁹ "The Board of Directors of the Posner Center of Justice for Pro Se's Nonprofit Corporation dissolved the Posner Center on July 23, 2019. The stated reason for the Posner Center's dissolution is that the Center was receiving many more requests for assistance from pro se litigants than it could handle. The mismatch was something on the order of 100 requests for assistance for every Center staff member." The Posner Center of Justice for Pro Se's: <http://www.justice-for-pro-ses.org/>

affirmative duty of judges to make findings of fact and law on the merits of the case, procedural deficiency notwithstanding: “Neutral engagement is an approach to cases involving self-represented litigants that permits the judge to make decisions based upon the merits of the case. . . . Judicial passivity, unlike neutral engagement, is ‘characterized by a responsive and reactive attitude, in which the judge does no more or less than acts as an umpire, responding only when asked to do so by counsel.’⁷⁵ . . . Neutral engagement, therefore, provides the fact-finder with as much evidence as reasonably possible to create a complete and reliable record to support the decision. . . . Decisions are based upon the merits of the case rather than a procedural or technical deficiency.” [70]

Case Assessment and Arbitration

The burden of justice rests with our three branches of government, particularly the courts, not with right-to-counsel attorneys pressured to get plea-bargain Stipulations. Resources to employ attorneys would be best spent on case by case assessment to serve fact-finding and arbitration in all cases:

1. Standardized good faith disclosure reports showing cause for filing of eviction complaint, property conditions, rental agreements, and financials of the parties to determine cost burden, certified by affidavit to the court, to judiciously identify the issues to be decided on the merits.
2. Mandatory arbitration of standardized good faith disclosures, resulting in resolution, would further reduce burden on the court and society.

Relief of Housing Security Burden on Manager Owners

Principle of Investment

The first objective of investing is to preserve the principal value of the investment. As we move toward a more openly transparent and machine-efficient economy, made possible by computing technology, it becomes more clearly obvious that land and housing resources are a unique asset class that must ultimately be managed as commons or quasi commons, and that open source computing makes inclusive decision-making for

⁷⁰ Wilson, D.J., Hutchins, M. B. (2015). Practical Advice from the Trenches: Best techniques for Handling Self-Represented Litigants. *Court Review* 51(2)
See [Disclosure](#); See notes [61] and [68b]

fair housing ownership and a safer, high quality of life technically trivial. For this reason, owners can play a vital role as property managers in public-private partnership, for preservation and innovation toward fair housing and cooperative workspaces that support ownership participation and community research and development.

1. Rather than speculate on trying to make a killing by forcing land and housing costs higher for capital gain, good property managers deserve good management fees, and understand that it is far safer and more predictable for everyone to avoid contributing to inequality and economic loss, where a passive capital gain is another's loss housing. Receiving reliable income from active management and open accounting practices unites owner managers and tenants in partnership with community, reducing conflict and economic instability.
2. Absentee homeowners who only rent one or two single family homes or apartments should consider divesting, unless they intend to actively engage in property management services and openly account for the cost burden of absentee ownership on the community.

Means and Merit Income

Rent controls, zoning, and wage-salary raises have been the primary strategies used by the wealthiest passive class to continue capturing the ownership and capital gains in land and housing at the expense of society, passing down just enough trickle-down to entice small investors into speculating on their very first absentee home purchase.^[71]

The inherent conflict between income and rising land and housing costs has again reached passive speculation limits and into the deep middle of the middle class. Cities everywhere are under crisis-level pressure to implement wage-salary increases and tenant protections.^[72] The pressure between absentee homeowners with one or two rental homes and their tenants has intensified to breakpoint, back and forth between the lower tiers of the barely-haves and the have-nots.

The non-profit Community Housing Improvement Program, a NYC property owner and management organization, has filed a civil rights lawsuit in response to The Housing Stability and Tenant Protection Act of 2019, enacted June 14, 2019. The lawsuit exemplifies how the divide and conquer strategy, pitting tenant against property owner,

⁷¹ See note [22]

⁷² 2020 Presidential Candidate Housing Plans. *Affordable Housing Online*.
<https://affordablehousingonline.com/2020-candidate-housing-plans>

and owner against tenant, has worked for the most wealthy passive barons and landlords for a long long time; leaving society fraught with setback after setback, never reaching the golden mean of means accounting and fair housing ownership for everyone.^[73]

The suit argues that there is no provision for periodic means accounting after a tenant initially qualifies for rent stabilized housing, and that failure to account for tenant financial means on a renewal basis implicates the financial means of the owner manager to maintain the property as housing price-costs rise, resulting in vacant units and blight. In a speculative housing market, where everyone needs housing security, small owner managers end up in the same sinking ship with their tenants and, once again, the wealthiest overlords get the life boats.^[74]

1. Under equal rights logic, financial means accounting applies to all parties equally. Open accounting for the income and expenses on all housing rental properties along with an annual financial statement from all parties who receive housing subsidies forms the basis for good faith public-private partnerships.
2. Merit accounting ensures that owner managers maintain building codes and maintenance standards, and that all units remain in rent-ready condition and listed as available when vacant.^[75]^[76]
3. Where owner managers show a financial cost burden to make necessary repairs or improvements, they should receive subsidy to make the necessary repairs and improvements, and vacancies could be subsidized to provide safe housing and economic inclusion for those who are homeless, unless the person is in need of special housing.
4. Upon transfer of ownership of the property, capital gains could be first allocated to repay subsidized repairs and improvements and then split pro rata between tenants after the owner manager receives the standard management fee from the capital gain, thus creating a public-private partnership between the public entity,

⁷³ Community Housing Improvement Program v. City of New York (1:19-cv-04087) District Court, E.D. New York

<https://www.courtlistener.com/recap/gov.uscourts.nyed.435882/gov.uscourts.nyed.435882.1.o.pdf>

⁷⁴ Martin, J., Strasburg, J. (2019, September 28). Why we're fighting rent laws in court. *New York Daily News*.

<https://www.nydailynews.com/opinion/ny-oped-why-were-fighting-rent-laws-in-court-20190928-nu3xak2pjvgp3buqqwixmajuu-story.html>

⁷⁵ Buhl, L. (2019, July 24). Can vacancy taxes bring down housing prices? *The American Prospect*.

<https://prospect.org/economy/can-vacancy-taxes-bring-housing-prices/>

⁷⁶ See note [49]

the property owner manager, and the tenant, bringing more housing into the public-private domain, and out of the speculative market, for improved access to fair housing ownership participation.

5. Means and merit accounting to the public should be immediately required of equity firms holding housing properties, and of all mortgage holders and homeowners in default, with a moratorium to prevent the sale of residential properties to absentee buyers, or for commercial use, until fair housing market assessments can be conducted by the public.

Relief of Housing Security Burden on Tenant Renters

Renting safe and affordable housing for 30% of one's gross income from cradle to grave, while being perpetually displaced from one house to another, and forced to pay moving expense and double rent for storage to avoid losing personal possessions, is not anything remotely close to fair housing ownership. "Safe and affordable," is the new euphemism for "fair housing,"^[77] that fateful Act of U.S. Congress on April 11, 1968, following the assassination of Rev. Dr. Martin Luther King Jr. seven days earlier on April the 4th.^[78] The ensuing riots persuaded Congress to finally pass the bill that President Johnson called, one of the "promises of a century... it proclaims that fair housing for all—all human beings who live in this country—is now a part of the American way of life." Xerox had just released the Magnafax Telecopier, a "brand" new 46-pound analog facsimile machine (1966), but it was still too easy to pad the numbers and shuffle the deck on fair housing dreams, and more than a half century hence, the dream of the means to fair housing ownership remains hidden in a revelation of the 19th century, recorded in the book of Job, or was it *Progress and Poverty*?

We're out of dream excuses and new revelations in 2020. Digital computing doesn't work in unseen ways. Accounting is integral to the code it runs, and reveals everything when you open the box and look at the instructions. Open accounting can connect and free us, or Surveillance Capitalism will manipulate, divide, and destroy us.^[79] Eviction law arises from the medieval feudal system of tally stick surveillance accounting of the

⁷⁷ <https://www.google.com/search?q=george+carlin+euphemisms>

⁷⁸ Uprety, A. (2019, January 21). Martin Luther King, Jr.'s fair housing legacy. *Equal Rights Center*. <https://equalrightscenter.org/martin-luther-king-fair-housing/>

⁷⁹ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power*. PublicAffairs. (See YouTube interviews.) See also note [48] on feudal eviction law in North Dakota.

unseen until-hard-felt hand of Mesne Lords upon Barons and Serfs from about 1100 until 1826.^[80] Participatory public-private accounting, on the other hand, is intrinsic to binary computing logic. Accountability is not a bug, it is the building code, making medieval eviction law superfluous.

Eviction

No one needs to be evicted in the digital age; as a matter of right; as a matter of fact. If it is a matter of means, means accounting can be instantly computed and adjusted to make budget shortage and surplus decisions frictionless, reducing healthcare costs, litigation, and social disruption across all indices. Where there is mismanagement, surplus means can be attached if absolutely necessary, although highly unlikely due to the accounting transparency that's built into the Housing Data System (HDS). Disputes are easily documented and resolved publicly.^[81] If the owner manager decides to divest, the burden rests equally with the owner and tenant because housing availability data is instantly accessible to everyone and rental applications are made and tracked via the HDS:

1. Rental applications are selected by sortition, based on prequalification, eliminating the possibility of unfairness and discrimination with regard to applicant selection.
2. Required rental agreements are standardized documents with conditions and restrictions stipulated by addendum in the HDS.
3. Vacancies and accounting entries on the HDS can be synchronized with owner manager and tenant accounting applications via open API, or entered directly via one's HDS account.
4. Notice with respect to relocation is at least three times more likely to be disruptive to the tenant than to the owner manager, suggesting that six month notice be given to the tenant and two month notice to the owner manager. In either case, HDS vacancy status can be automatically updated and the housing unit made available in real time to the public.
5. Reporting of need for service repairs or maintenance is quick and easy via HDS.

⁸⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tally_stick and the tally stick burning of Westminster Palace in 1834. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mesne_lord | See note [51]

⁸¹ Rare cases could require compulsory process and special housing based on HDS data and clear and convincing evidence.

6. In the interim to HDS deployment, the principles of HDS computing logic should be secured by due process. No eviction is lawful without findings of fact on good faith cause, balancing cost burden, the availability of housing, and sufficient time to relocate to comparable housing and to divest of surplus property if downsizing.

Dispossession

The dispossession and liquidation of personal property as a result of cost burden or eviction without good faith cause, is a degrading disgrace to human dignity. It is severely consequential to social relations, disrupts productivity and personal development, causes PTSD-related health problems, and lost employment and life opportunities. It undermines confidence in community and the capacity for fair governance, economy and culture. On this premise, liquidation of personal property was long ago prohibited by R.I.G.L. § 9-26-4 and § 9-26-12, which remains the controlling intent of law, in that personal property is first and foremost a fundamental life necessity belonging to the tenant prior to seizure of the landlord via writ of the eviction court.

When a lord is allowed to evict a serf and confiscates the tenant's property, the tenant accepts whatever smaller and cheaper or more expensive housing is available, and pays double for storage and moving fees, or is forced to forfeit one's most sentimental valuables at auction. Does the tenant have a property interest right to the capital gain from the rent value invested into the home that was not maintained before being shoved out? Unfortunately not, but should anyone be double and triple charged for rent space and moving expense in order to keep their clothes and bedding and bibles?^[82]

These so-called "public auctions," under color of commercial warehouse law, are not openly published and searchable online, and apparently only known to the insiders who bulk-buy tenant property that was seized and randomly packed and stacked in boxes, to then sell item by item on ebay or in their local discount store,^[83] perpetuating the cycle of predatory eviction and dispossession in an absentee homeowner's market, where only institutional and industry actors have access to the data.

⁸² "Particularly in cases where property placed in self-storage is the result of economic hardship, such as divorce, homelessness, or illness, there is a public interest in ensuring that auctions conform with something similar to due process . . . the legal process which the common law of property has long required prior to dispossessing people of what they own." Jones, J. (2011). Property rights, property wrongs, and chattel dispossession under self-storage leases. *Tennessee Law Review*, 78(4), 1015-1050.

⁸³ Larrabee, J. (2011, July 20). Auction lures treasure hunters to Blackstone Valley Self Storage. *Patch*. <https://patch.com/rhode-island/woonsocket/auction-lures-treasure-hunters-to-blackstone-valley-s289e9b761e>

Therefore:

1. The public has a right to online access of all public auction data, bills of lading, auction dates, lien holders, bidding and buyer parties, bills of sale, etc., related to the forced liquidation of personal property under commercial law.
2. There is no such irrational contradiction in HDS protocol that allows for dispossession and liquidation of personal property, and any notice of a "commercial auction" involving personal property can be reported and prevented.
3. Executive and legislative action should be taken immediately to prevent any person from being deprived of their personal property, per the imperative of R.I.G.L. § 9-26-4 and § 9-26-12; which presupposes that liquidation of one's personal property under the Uniform Commercial Code (UUC) or Warehouse Receipt Act, by "commercial society," as Adam Smith called it, ^[84] is of greater cost and consequence to organic society than any cost to the public to safeguard the transfer of one's personal property from one rental house to the next.

Participation

The outcome of the Fair Housing Act was not fair housing, but segregation through NIMBY zoning. Fair housing ownership became segregated "public" housing that was not community owned or managed; without infrastructure for local economy, requiring everyone to commute for substandard wages in gentrified business districts; creating two very separate worlds: one that could not possibly work, and one to where everyone traveled to work.^[85] Since 2008, corporate media has manufactured consent to encourage everyone to forget about fair housing ownership and settle for "safe and affordable" segregated rental housing.^[86] Shall we once again circumvent the issues of class inequality and discrimination in order to perpetuate divisive isolationist policies that prevent participation and home ownership in a fair economy?

1. Having safe and affordable housing, fairly owned and managed by resident-participants in partnership with community, with open access to healthcare and education and a living income that provisions 10% pension

⁸⁴ See note [7]

⁸⁵ Rothstein, R. (2017). *The Color of Law. A Forgotten History of How Our Government Segregated America*. LiveRight.

⁸⁶ Chomsky, N., Herman, E. (1988). *Manufacturing Consent: The Political Economy of the Mass Media*. Pantheon Books.

savings and the means to save 10% of gross income for personal investment, in exchange for fair participation in economic development, infrastructure and culture, would probably be a good place to start for a 2020 new deal.^[87]

2. President Franklin D. Roosevelt's bailout tax on the most wealthy, —wealth that had been taken from society— returned to society the ability to fund a more participatory economy, which helped alleviate poverty and inequality without affecting in the slightest the lifestyles of those who gave back very little, actually, of what they had taken in the first place.
3. With full participation in public-private partnership for access and accountability toward greater fairness and cooperation, everyone might begin to feel better about living a better quality of life together.

Conclusions

Freedom is only found in fairness. If we are not equally free, conflict ensues that affects everyone. We cannot fully enjoy the benefits of digital computing without accounting publically for the resource values that determine fair economic outcomes. Fairness can only be determined by accounting for the facts that make it possible to balance the interests of all parties.

The most universal self-interest of all parties is time. (“From dust thou art to dust thou shalt return.”) Free time is determined by how much time we should each contribute to community infrastructure and cultural development, in order to sustain most equally a high standard of living. We all require the same nutrition. We each only occupy one bed, one room, one house and one set of lonely shoes at a time.

We all have on average the same genes that require similar healthcare. We all have on average the same intelligence that requires similar education time, unless traumatized by imposed scarcity; and we all have the same need for fair access to land, water, clean air, shelter and transportation. To avoid these fundamental issues of personal time and freedom with dismissive clichés like Capitalism, Socialism, Libertarianism, or any Otherism, is to fundamentally disregard how individuals, communities and nation-states, to which these cliché labels are often attached, actually operate in practice, as referenced briefly in this paper.

The public information we need for inclusive decision-making on fair housing, as a unique public asset class, already exists behind corporate paywalls in the privileged

⁸⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/New_Deal

private databases of the Surveillance Capitalism class.^[88] How can it be fair to socialize the cost of private privilege and passive wealth, through corporate welfare bailouts, while withholding information from the public, at the expense of the majority who are most cost burdened by the policies requiring the bailouts?^[89]

The overlapping consensus with respect to the accounting logic upon which all activity in time and place is based and computed, emphasizes that we can't manage the numbers of numbers we can't access and verify. The big question remains unanswered— When and how will we provide open access accounting for inclusive participation and fairness in the management of the natural resources upon which we all equally depend, by which our capacity for economy and culture is determined?^[90]

Policy Priorities

Relief for Those Most Burdened

Take immediate executive and legislative action to stop the irreparable harm of the dispossession of personal property, under commercial color of law, that adds insult to injury of both victim and community.

Take immediate executive, legislative, and judicial action to prevent eviction, by accounting publically for good faith cause, and the cost burden of relocation on all parties, to guarantee procedural due process of findings on the merits, for the fair housing interests of all parties.

Relief for Community Development and Culture

Take immediate executive and legislative action to develop an open source Housing Data System as described herein, to provide public access and accounting for inclusive public-private participation, using the public data that is currently made available only to corporate-state actors, and to require the sourcing and use of such additional public data needed to implement and maintain an HDS platform. In the interim, provide open access to all existing public-private partnership data on existing public and public-private platforms, i.e., EFS, CoreLogic, open API, etc..

⁸⁸ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power*. PublicAffairs. (See YouTube interviews.)

⁸⁹ Brennan, M., Blumenthal, P., Goodman, L., Seidman, E., & Meixell, B. (2017). Housing as an Asset Class: Opportunities for Systems Change to Enhance Social Equity and Inclusion. *Urban Institute*. http://www.urban.org/sites/default/files/publication/93601/housing-as-an-asset-class_1.pdf

⁹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Overlapping_consensus

Disclosure

My partner, Silvia Oliveira, PhD., and I were evicted on October 2, 2018, from 18 Sheffield Avenue, North Providence, RI 02911; no delinquency of rent, without good faith cause, and without due process of court findings on the issues of our rental agreement of seven years. We were displaced into a chaotic state of transitional homelessness, without lease security for a very long year, until October 1, 2019. We now remain in crisis from the dispossession of nearly all of our personal property, currently held by the landlord, (employed by Providence Housing Authority) and hired commercial agent, Jones Moving and Storage.

We were forced to rent month-to-month at 4 Walker Street, Lincoln, RI 02865, to endure faulty appliances and fire code violations documented by the Town of Lincoln, where in retaliation we were evicted after seven months by a pro se landlord-attorney. With no delinquency of rent and without good faith cause, we were forced by circumstance to settle our counterclaim under duress and vacate on May 31, 2019.

We camped at Holiday Acres Campground, 593 Snake Hill Rd., North Scituate, RI 02857, from June 2, until October 15, 2019. Between April and late September of 2019, we visited many dozens of properties seeking to either rent or purchase, made loan prequalification applications and preliminary offers to purchase, and submitted multiple applications to rent houses and apartments unsuccessfully. Believe it or not, we were even denied entry by the landlord's sister, when we tried to view and consider making a timely purchase offer on our rental residence of seven years, following her listing of the house for sale nine months after we were evicted, having made only cosmetic improvements to the property while it remained vacant over the winter, and we were homeless without housing security. We finally secured a lease agreement on a house in Warwick beginning October 1, 2019.

At our eviction, October 2, 2018, we were dispossessed of ninety-nine percent of our personal belongings, on watch of the North Providence Police Department, including all bedding, clothing, culinary and medical needs equipment, perishables, family bibles and children's property and educational books, family heirlooms and artwork, and research and development tools of trade, etc., insured at the time of eviction by a renter's policy of \$30,000 dollars for minimum coverage; protected from attachment and liquidation by R.I.G.L. § 9-26-4 and § 9-26-12.

We have been in and out of District and Superior Court since August of 2018, seeking relief on the merits of the case and to recover our personal belongings. The Attorney General is aware of our case, and we will once again be seeking relief as soon as physically possible in the Rhode Island Supreme Court, on due process grounds that not a single issue raised was heard by the District or Superior courts, and that it is the affirmative duty of the appointed judges of Rhode Island to make findings of fact and law on the issues raised as a matter of due process, and to procedurally ensure that all parties are heard on the merits; or otherwise find for the record clear and convincing evidence of an unwillingness to participate, before denying procedurally any party the right to findings of fact and law on the merits.

For a year and a half we continue in a state of emergency without access to our personal property for over sixteen months, after being twice evicted and having lived in a passenger van for over four months. When one loses housing security, including all personal-needs and family possessions, everything, including mental health, personal relationships, and trust in community, is on the line. We are now in receipt of notice that our personal property will be sold by commercial auction on Thursday, February 13, 2020, at 1:00 P.M., at Jones Moving & Storage, 59 Central Street, Providence, RI 02907-2293.

I can be reached for interview and collaboration at kurt@1bite.com or by phone at 224-241-2483, and by direct message on most Surveillance Capital "social" platforms.

Case documents can be accessed for public review and comment at the following repositories:

[Academia.edu](https://independent.academia.edu/KurtBrenneman)

<https://independent.academia.edu/KurtBrenneman>

[Google Drive](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1K6xxLFfesR5gmxxvQYFbqOieiVZIAIhGN?usp=sharing)

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1K6xxLFfesR5gmxxvQYFbqOieiVZIAIhGN?usp=sharing>

[Dropbox](https://www.dropbox.com/sh/c82x5g01w4e22fx/AAA9OJZ29J18Xo1nL6IXBRRva?dl=0)

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/c82x5g01w4e22fx/AAA9OJZ29J18Xo1nL6IXBRRva?dl=0>

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